

Participatory Toolkit

BRITE Box Project

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Contents

1. BRITE box project	1
1.1 Context of the problem the project is addressing	1
1.2 The project	1
1.3 The method	2
1.4 Methodological literature review	3
2. What we did	5
2.1 Participant selection	5
2.2 Interviews	5
2.3 Data analysis	6
2.4 Ethical considerations	6
2.5 Bias reduction & participant relationships	6
2.6 What we learned	7
3. Getting started	10
3.1 Embedding participatory methods: A step-by-step guide	10
3.2 Steps 1 and 2: Identifying & engaging stakeholders	10
3.3 Step 3: Ethical considerations & best practice	12
3.4 Steps 4-6: Design and agree research aims, objectives & methods, data collection & analysis	12
3.5 Steps 5 and 6: Data collection & analysis	14
3.6 Step 7: Present results to stakeholders and community	14
3.7 Conclusions & recommendations	14
References	16
Appendix 1: Participatory toolkit interview questions	19

1. BRITE box project

1.1 Context of the problem the project is addressing

Food insecurity (FI) affected an estimated 14.8% of UK households in January 2024 (Food Foundation, 2024), having increased during the pandemic and subsequent cost-of-living crisis (Chaudhuri et al, 2024). It describes lack of regular access to adequate safe and nutritious food to enable health and optimal growth and development (FAO, 1983). FI affects some groups more than others. One such group is families with children – approximately a quarter of families with children are food insecure, and it is four times as common in more deprived compared with less deprived households (Food Foundation, 2024). Other high-risk groups are Black, Asian and minority ethnic groups (BAME) as well as those with disability (Food Foundation, 2024). Those with FI tend to have less nutritious diets (French et al, 2019; PHE, 2019; PHE & FSA, 2020), which affects their long-term health and wellbeing since diet is a major modifiable risk factor for chronic disease (WHO, 2023). FI is driven by lack of money rather than lack of food (Bramley et al, 2021; Trussell Trust, 2022; Power et al, 2021; Bull et al, 2023). Therefore FI sits at an intersection of risks – poor or insecure income and access to food, increasing risk of ill-health. These are directly relevant to the poverty and deprivation as well as the health improvement themes of the London Met Lab. Within London, only 51% say they have enough money to manage while 39% say they struggle to get by. This is largely due to energy costs (56% saying this was unaffordable), but food prices were also highlighted as unaffordable by 31% (Cottrell et al, 2023). Similarly to the more recent data from the Food Foundation, those with a child under 18 years, those renting their homes and those with a disability were more likely to find food prices unaffordable. One in nine had used a food bank in the previous month (Cottrell et al, 2023). Reducing FI is a priority of the London Food Plan (Greater London Authority, 2018).

1.2 The project

BRITE Box (Building Resilience in Today's Environment) is a project providing free recipe kits to children and families. The initiative was founded in 2020 by the Voices of Hope charity in partnership with KingsGate Church. Eligible children are largely identified as being at risk of FI by their school, though some children also receive a box if they have a limited diet or are 'fussy' or selective eaters (Voices of Hope, 2023). Boxes are now delivered to over 30 partner schools across 11 UK locations (Voices of Hope, 2025). The recipe boxes provided by BRITE Box aim to bring families together by providing nutritionally adequate recipes designed for children to cook with their family which are also appropriate e.g. vegetarian and gluten-free options available (Mulrooney and Ranta, 2024).

BRITE Box recipes were analysed and compared to the government standards for school food (Department for Education, 2025) and the nutrient-based guidelines for children’s after-school meals (Crawley, 2005). The results suggested that the boxes met all government standards, and were broadly within or above the nutrient-based guidelines for after-school meals. As such, the recipe boxes were deemed nutritionally adequate and of particular benefit was the availability of fresh fruits and vegetables, the opportunity for children to learn to cook, and the encouragement of family bonding (Bhakta et al., 2023).

In a 2022 evaluation, 93.6% of respondents had a positive experience with BRITE Box, and 74.1% said it helped with their food budgeting (Ranta et al., 2022). A follow-up evaluation in 2023 found similar results. The allocation of BRITE Boxes is decided locally within individual schools, so that a wide range of children with differing needs receive the boxes and the duration of the scheme also varies – whole academic year in some, term-time in others (Ranta et al., 2022).

1.3 The method

Table 1 outlines the aim & objectives of the participatory toolkit research, as well as a broad outline of the methods used. These are detailed in the following sections.

Aim	Objectives	Methods
To investigate the BRITE Box evaluations, identifying the methods and approaches utilised to facilitate participatory research and community engagement.	To create a comprehensive participatory research toolkit informed by the insights and outcomes of the BRITE Box evaluations	Collaborative case study approach with participants using interviews & pre-designed interview guide to explore their perspectives. Key participants who led the 2022 and 2023 evaluations were identified and invited to participate in this study.
	To enhance collaborative research practices and community engagement within the discipline	Thematic analysis of interviews to identify key themes and subthemes (Braun & Clarke, 2006), analysing the outcome of interviews to create an initial toolkit design. An inductive approach was used to identify key themes. These were identified through familiarisation with interviews by repeated listening. Patterns were

		coded and grouped into themes & subthemes.
		A cyclical iterative approach to interview analysis was used to create the initial toolkit design.
		A sense-check of the toolkit with key participant/s was undertaken to ensure its utility.

Table 1: Aim, objectives & methods used to develop the participatory research toolkit

1.4 Methodological literature review

In the UK, the number of people in food insecure households increased from 4.7 million to 7.2 million in the financial year 2022/23, equivalent to 11% of the population and 17% of children (Frances-Devine, 2024). Academics have been encouraged to shift their research agendas to focus on forming relationships and partnerships with communities experiencing FI, utilising community voices to guide positive action and advocate for change (Pine and de Souza, 2013). Participatory research involves partnering with communities or organisations to design and implement research which is beneficial to the community (Israel et al., 2005). This methodology involves the cyclical development of shared aims and objectives to achieve outcomes of value to the community being studied (Berge et al., 2009). This approach allows research to have real-world impacts, whilst academics gain context and understanding about the community which they can take forward in future research.

A large body of evidence exists within the U.S. A study of African American adults utilised participatory methods to identify food insecure groups and to assess the extent of FI within that community (Paschal et al., 2020). Results of questionnaires identified that 55.9% of the participants were food insecure and authors were concerned with the quantity of fresh fruits and vegetables consumed, which was less than 1 portion per day (Paschal et al., 2020). The authors credited the participatory approach for allowing them easier access to this vulnerable and disadvantaged group and praised the engagement of the community partners throughout their research.

Another study conducted a survey in partnership with BronxWorks, a community-based organisation who aided in the expansion of food pantry services in conjunction with other services such as financial, health and housing support (Azhar et al., 2023). The goal of the survey was to identify the predictors of FI and childhood hunger, and stakeholders were involved in the review, selection and design of the survey questions. Results identified high levels of food insecurity with a Household Food Security Survey score of 3.43 (US Department of Agriculture, 2012), however families remain threatened with FI even in receipt of food pantry parcels and those with more than one child in the household, those experiencing depression or those

without health insurance were particularly at risk (Azhar et al., 2023). In similar community-based participatory research within Native American communities, participants identified barriers including racial injustice, inadequate finances and geographic isolation (Blue Bird Jernigan et al., 2011). The participatory approach taken resulted in the development of walking and cycling paths, adjustments to supermarket layout and improved availability of culturally appropriate food – all interventions driven by community needs (Blue Bird Jernigan et al., 2011).

In the UK, one study engaged with four “social eating initiatives”, identifying their views, needs, challenges and impact through informal conversations (Luca et al., 2023). The findings indicated that surplus food enterprises played a positive role in improving FI and access to nutritious, homemade foods. Moreover, the use of participatory methods within this study uncovered that social eating experiences leverage the social value of food, moving beyond simply alleviating FI (Luca et al., 2023). The Grange, a community-led garden in Blackpool, co-designed research with Jackson and Ronzi (2021) to identify the impact of the initiative on health, well-being and inclusion. Utilising photovoice methods, this participatory research identified that the community garden improved financial and geographic access to fresh fruits and vegetables, however further activities were needed for teenagers and elderly people to improve the reach of the project (Jackson and Ronzi, 2021). In this case, the use of participatory methods identified important outcomes and improvements for the project to further benefit the community served.

Focusing on FI in children, Jarrott et al. (2021) created partnerships with childcare centres in neighbourhoods that serve families at risk of FI, utilising the snowball technique to identify a variety of stakeholders. These stakeholders drove the development and implementation of a nutrition education programme ‘Food for a Long Life’. Whilst the authors noted difficulties in engaging stakeholders such as parents, the flexibility of participatory approaches were credited for helping to shape their programme which resulted in improved eating behaviours of pre-school children (Jarrott et al., 2021).

2. What we did

A case study approach was used in this study, which followed the key principles of participatory action research. Collaboration with the participants was emphasised to create outcomes which would best meet the requirements of the academic community when conducting future participatory research. The research followed a cyclical process, whereby the outcomes of interviews were analysed to create an initial toolkit design. Feedback from one key stakeholder was sought to ensure it was fit for purpose and reflected the views of the community. Further edits and refinements were then made in response to the feedback before a final review.

2.1 Participant selection

Participants for the participatory toolkit research were identified using purposive sampling, since they were required to have been part of the research team for the BRITE Box evaluations. This means they were intentionally sought and identified from their previous involvement. They included the leaders of the BRITE Box organisation, who had co-designed the evaluation tools. A total of seven participants were contacted, of whom four agreed to be interviewed. Initial contact was made via email and informed consent was gained.

2.2 Interviews

Interviews were semi-structured, with a list of pre-determined open-ended questions (see Appendix 1) to use as prompts, which allowed for exploration of topics that arose during the interviews. The questions were flexible and, depending on the participants' previous answers, adapted to best suit the flow of the interview or applicability of the question. Whilst this method made it more difficult to compare responses across participants, the structure of the initial questions ensured key topics were still addressed. This allowed for a balance of structure required for the thematic analysis, and flexibility to allow the participants to feel comfortable sharing a range of opinions relevant to the creation of the toolkit.

Questions were structured through first asking what the participant did as part of their research, and following this asking them to reflect on these choices and whether they were successful, unsuccessful, and whether there were any choices they would have changed on reflection.

They were also asked to think about future research options and how they would implement participatory approaches.

Interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams and were audio recorded and transcribed manually to ensure an accurate account of the interview was obtained. These transcriptions were double-checked by the researcher whilst listening to the audio recording to ensure the transcription was accurate.

2.3 Data analysis

Thematic analysis, adapted from Braun and Clarke (2006) was used to analyse the interviews due to its flexibility whilst maintaining rigor when understanding the subjective experiences of the participants (Riger and Sigurvinsdottir, 2016; Banyard and Miller, 1998). Analysis began with familiarisation when transcribing the audio recordings, of crucial importance due to the inductive approach adopted. Transcription was completed manually, listening once to complete the draft transcription and a second time to confirm there were no errors within the transcripts. Pattern coding was then completed to capture key sentiments within the text which were grouped to determine the main themes. Transcripts were read twice to confirm no key sentiments were missed, and the number of participants who mentioned these sentiments was recorded. These themes represented the significant patterns and insights of the data, which were used to create the toolkit.

2.4 Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was gained from the London Metropolitan University Research Ethics Committee prior to commencing any research or communicating with participants. Informed consent was gained both in writing and verbally. Recordings and transcripts were securely saved online in password-protected folders accessible only to the research team, and were deleted at the end of the project.

To maintain equity throughout, the toolkit was created using the participants' responses based on their own research, with additional review against the literature where necessary. Interview responses were not shared with participants to avoid influencing one another and maintain confidentiality (due to the small group of interviewees and the fact that they had all worked together on the BRITE Box research). Communication remained open during analysis and the final review of the toolkit was governed by one lead participant as a representative of the group to facilitate efficient feedback due to the time constraints of this study.

2.5 Bias reduction & participant relationships

The researcher, having previously volunteered for BRITE Box and with the intention to do so again, recognised the potential for bias in favour of their work and support of the evaluations conducted by the research team. It was therefore essential to maintain objectivity and carefully critique the methods selected by the participants when designing the toolkit.

Within the analysis, transcripts were first anonymised and referred to as numbers thereafter to avoid bias. A systematic approach was taken to coding and identifying key themes to ensure all transcripts were analysed consistently. Once finalised, the analysis and toolkit were shared with the lead participant to discuss findings and validate the outcomes to ensure they reflected the general opinions of

the group. Purposive sampling (see above) to capture the views of the research team ensured representation and the avoidance of a skew towards stronger opinions.

In addition, there was potential for power dynamics to play a part, particularly since those interviewed all had significant and ongoing roles within the project – some as organisers, others as volunteers or researchers. Participants did not see or hear about the responses of other participants and an interview guide was used to ensure consistency between interviews. In addition, recording the interviews ensured that any potential power imbalance could be identified. Power dynamics were not highlighted as problematic within this project, but are worth actively monitoring in other projects.

2.6 What we learned

The major themes identified from the research were community collaboration, ethical considerations and iterative development of the research tools (Table 2). Community collaboration was the most frequently mentioned theme. This included aspects important for participatory research; identification & engagement of the key stakeholders to build relationships, decision-making shared between the researchers and the stakeholders with mutual benefit and co-design. Ethical working was also highlighted to ensure that bias was identified and work was transparent. Within this theme the importance of mutual benefit was also alluded to but in this context, the responsibility was to ensure that the work benefited the communities involved (not just the researchers). In relation to the development of the research tools, responsive development which adapted to feedback and was tailored to the needs of the community under investigation was highlighted. Additional but smaller themes were the need for adaptability (in relation both to methods used and the continuous development of tools), and research which focused on real-world impact.

Theme	Codes	Code count	Theme count
Community collaboration	Building relationships	3	14
	Co-design	4	
	Shared decision-making	2	
	Stakeholder identification and engagement	3	
	Mutually beneficial outcomes	2	
Ethical considerations	Bias	3	7
	Transparency	2	
	Responsibility - must benefit community	2	
Impact-oriented research	Real-world impact	4	4
Iterative development of research tools	Feedback loops	3	7
	Learning and adapting	3	
	Customisation to suit community in practice	1	
Adaptability	Methodological flexibility	3	5
	Continuous improvement	2	

Table 2: Themes and codes identified within thematic analysis

From this, a number of recommendations for participatory research were made (Table 3). These broad recommendations are suitable for all those considering the use of participatory approaches to their work.

Toolkit Element	Description	Relevant Insights
Flexibility	The toolkit must be flexible and applicable to various contexts.	Importance of generalisability.
Reflection	Users should reflect on their motivation to use participatory approaches.	Align intentions with project goals.
List of methodologies	A comprehensive list of potential methodologies should be included.	Options tailored to different research projects.
Consultation with community	Researchers should not pre-determine methodologies before consulting with the community or organisation to ensure methods used are appropriate to their context.	Ensures collaboration and shared decision-making.
Stakeholder identification and engagement	Identifying and engaging with key stakeholders within the community or organisation is crucial to this approach.	Understanding of community dynamics and cultural context.
Being open to feedback	Researchers must remain open to feedback and criticism when developing methods.	Improving the research. Meeting the research aims and objectives.
Communication structure and frequency	Establishing clear communication pathways and meeting frequently is necessary.	Facilitates collaboration and trusting relationships.
Step-by-Step Guide	An overview of the development of participatory research should be included.	Clear direction and structure for those new to the methodology.

Table 3: Participatory research toolkit recommendations

3. Getting started

Before undertaking participatory research, reflect on why you want to use a participatory approach. Think about your reasoning for this approach, and whether it is well intentioned.

3.1 Embedding participatory methods: A step-by-step guide

The following guide (Figure 1) highlights the key steps to take within participatory research and collaborative work with communities:

Figure 1: Key steps in the development of participatory research

3.2 Steps 1 and 2: Identifying & engaging stakeholders

Of particular importance within this process is the relationship with and engagement of key stakeholders within the community/organisation. This relationship will be the foundation that the research is built upon and will help to establish an open and trusting environment where ideas can be exchanged, and best practices established. It will aid in the development of research objectives and the identification and engagement of participants from the wider community. It is important to ensure that there is a diverse range of stakeholders involved to ensure a range of views are taken into account.

To promote effective communication during participatory research, avoid using jargon or complex terminology to ensure clarity during discussions. Actively seek feedback from community partners to understand their perspectives and ensure understanding. Researchers should also consider adapting tone and formality to align

with community preferences, fostering a collaborative and respectful environment that supports mutual understanding and engagement.

Throughout all communications, researchers should manage the expectations of the community by being clear, concise and reinforcing expectations throughout the study. Accountability should be established, and any uncertainties should be proactively managed and communicated transparently. It may be beneficial to document agreements or decisions more formally, or summarise by email, to confirm understanding and avoid misinterpretation.

- Familiarise yourself with the community's history, culture, values and challenges.
- Map out key individuals, organisations and groups who may already be engaged in the area you would like to research. This could include NGOs, charities, community leaders, residents or councils.
- Reach out to stakeholders informally via phone, email or at a community event or meeting. Introduce yourself and your wish to collaborate.

- Understand the concerns, experiences and priorities of the stakeholders.
- Clarify your intentions, the research process, and what each stakeholder's role will be in the research.
- Agree and outline the project, roles and responsibilities formally - ensure equitable contribution.
- Establish a schedule for regular meetings to update stakeholders on progress and gather feedback - be flexible and adjust the research as necessary.

Figure 2: Engagement and communication with stakeholders

It is important to establish roles at the outset of the research to ensure all participants are clear and have undergone sufficient training, for example in collecting and storing data using particular methodologies. It is vital that all participants maintain high standards and rigour within data collection to ensure reliable results and outcomes. The following section will detail a range of methodologies which can be applied in participatory research, with further information which may aid decision-making at this stage.

3.3 Step 3: Ethical considerations & best practice

It may be necessary to seek ethics approval for the research. Even if not, work should be aligned with ethical principles and best practice. Whether acknowledged or not, researchers are likely to have an ethical position or bias towards their research projects. In addition to standard ethical principles of research, it is of particular significance to be mindful of the following:

1. Power dynamics
2. Cultural sensitivity
3. Inclusivity and diversity
4. Sustainable (long term) impact of research and engagement
5. Flexibility and adaptability whilst maintaining methodological rigour (Wilson et al., 2018; Kwan and Walsh, 2018).

3.4 Steps 4-6: Design and agree research aims, objectives & methods, data collection & analysis

Multiple meetings with stakeholders are likely to be needed to discuss and agree the aims and objectives of the research and to explore potential methodologies.

When considering potential methodologies, it is important to consider how they will be applied within the specific context, and to identify barriers that may make application more challenging. Most methodologies can be participatory if they are collaboratively developed and implemented with the organisation or community. As such, the following table is not an exhaustive list but rather a list of key methods and considerations to keep in mind (Table 4).

Method	Applications	Considerations	Resources required
Interviews	One-to-one interview e.g. structured or semi-structured with questions	Time to transcribe interviews	Trained facilitators Audio recording devices/ software (if applicable)
Questionnaires/ surveys	Questions distributed and answered online or physically to gather a large amount of data on a particular topic	Access to technology Education levels of the community Response rate	Online survey tools (if applicable) Access to printing facilities (if applicable)
Focus groups	Small group discussions of a specific topic with 5-6 participants, guided by a moderator to understand attitudes and opinions	Cultural sensitivities & differences of opinion Group dynamics & potential dominance	Trained facilitators/moderators Meeting space Audio recording devices or software (if applicable)
Participant observation	Direct observation of participants in their natural settings to gather data (e.g. dietary behaviours, eating practices, food preparation)	Observer bias Ethical considerations (privacy, consent) Hawthorne effect	Skilled observers with cultural awareness Additional time
Photo elicitation/ Photovoice	Using photographs during an interview or focus group to provoke	Interpretation may vary among participants Ethical considerations if using personal or sensitive images	Participant access to camera or photographs Display tools (e.g. printer, projector)

	<p>discussion, reflection and insights. In the case of Photovoice, these photographs should be of significant items, people or places</p>		
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Table 4: Qualitative methodologies for use in participatory research

Whilst participatory research typically utilises qualitative methods to gain context and perspectives of the community, quantitative methods (such as food diaries) can be used with this approach provided the community agrees that these methods will aid in delivering actionable outcomes (Duke, 2020).

Methods should not be chosen without consulting the community or organisation who are co-designers of the research. Their insights will guide and improve participation. It is important to remain open to co-designer’s feedback and criticisms when designing methods such as interview questions and surveys as they will have a deeper knowledge of cultural sensitivities which may not have been considered.

3.5 Steps 5 and 6: Data collection & analysis

Data collection should be carried out taking into account the needs of the community under investigation and using the tools agreed with stakeholders. How these are implemented within specific communities needs also to be agreed with stakeholders. The specific population must be considered prior to data collection (e.g. are translators needed? Can data be collected face-to-face or online?). Dissemination routes for tools such as questionnaires or invitations to participate should be informed by the stakeholders who can advise on what will work best within the specific context.

3.6 Step 7: Present results to stakeholders and community

Findings should be shared with those who have contributed to the work. This ensures that the work is non-extractive but also enables input into future directions and next steps. How this is done will be context-specific and should be informed by the stakeholders who will know what will work best for their community.

3.7 Conclusions & recommendations

Cultivating strong, trust-based relationships with community partners is fundamental to the success of participatory research. Clear articulation of research intentions, a commitment to avoiding extractive practices and aligning with the community’s priorities fosters sustained collaboration and partnership and produces mutually beneficial

outcomes. Once a trusting relationship has been established, it is important not to do things that the stakeholders or co-designers are uncomfortable with and ensure that the research direction aligns with the outcomes the community requested.

Managing expectations through transparent communication enhances accountability and reduces the likelihood of misinterpretation. Remaining flexible and adaptable throughout further facilitates equitable decision-making. Future research should consider longer term impact studies to assess the sustained impact of participatory approaches and tools on community outcomes. The broader application and refinement of the toolkit in a variety of community settings should be considered for iterative improvement. As with any research, it is likely that unforeseen challenges will arise during participatory research. To limit the impact of these challenges, strategies should be adjusted as required, remaining flexible and adaptable at all times. To address issues promptly, maintain open communication with research partners within the community, and collaborate on solutions to support equitable decision-making throughout.

Participatory research engages communities in designing and implementing studies that address their needs, offering real-world impact while providing researchers with important contextual insights. Key steps include stakeholder engagement, clear role definitions, and method selection, such as interviews, questionnaires, or focus groups, with attention to ethical considerations and community feedback. Building trust, clear communication, and flexibility are vital for aligning research with community goals and addressing challenges. Researchers should ensure methods and outcomes are mutually beneficial and uphold ethical standards. The continued publication of participatory research experiences will aid in advancing best practices and will continue to contribute to the collective knowledge in this field.

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Appendix 1: Participatory toolkit interview questions

General Questions

1. How did you first become involved in the evaluation of BRITE Box?
2. What was your role in the evaluation of BRITE Box?
3. Can you describe the overall aim and objectives of the BRITE Box evaluation?
4. What was your primary motivation for adopting participatory research methods in this instance?
5. What is your 'research ethos'? How do you approach research?

Development and Implementation of Methods

1. What participatory research methods were utilised during the BRITE Box evaluation, and why were these specific methods chosen?
2. Can you walk me through the process of developing these methods?
3. Were there any particular frameworks or models that guided your research approach?

Facilitating Community Engagement

1. How did you identify and engage key stakeholders and community members to participate in the research?
2. Did you employ any particular strategies to ensure meaningful and inclusive participation?
3. Can you share any specific challenges you faced in engaging these stakeholders / the community and how you addressed them?
4. Were there any methods of engagement that you did not use that, in hindsight, you believe you should have? Perhaps you have used these methods in more recent research and have found them beneficial?

Reflection on Outcomes and Impact

1. How did participatory methods influence the outcomes of the BRITE Box evaluation?
2. Can you provide examples of how community input directly impacted the research findings or outcomes?
3. What were the most significant benefits of using participatory methods in this evaluation?

Lessons Learned and Best Practices

1. What key lessons did you learn about the use of participatory research methods from this project?

2. Were there any unexpected outcomes or insights gained through the use of participatory methods?
3. What advice would you give to other researchers looking to incorporate participatory methods into their work?

Developing the Toolkit

1. Based on your experience, what are the essential components that you think should be included in a participatory research toolkit?
2. Can you share any specific tools or resources that were particularly useful in your participatory research process?

Future Directions

1. How do you envision the future of participatory research evolving based on your experiences with the BRITE Box project?
2. Are there any ongoing or future projects that you plan to implement using the participatory methods refined in the BRITE Box evaluation?

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